

Buckling of a Timoshenko beam bonded to an elastic half-plane: Effects of sharp and smooth beam edges

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Abstract

The problem of a compressed Timoshenko beam of finite length in frictionless contact with an elastic half-plane is analytically investigated here. The problem formulation leads to an integro-differential equation that can be transformed into an algebraic system by expanding the rotation of the beam cross sections in series of Chebyshev polynomials. An eigenvalue problem is then obtained, whose solution provides the buckling loads of the beam and, in turn, the corresponding mode shapes. Beams with sharp or smooth edges are considered in detail, founding relevant differences. In particular, it is shown that beams with smooth edges cannot exhibit a rigid-body critical mode. Finally, based on the Galin solution for the rigid flat punch on a half-plane, a simple relation between the elastic modulus of a half-plane and the subgrade constant of a Winkler foundation is found, thus providing a straightforward formula predicting the buckling loads of rigid beams resting on elastic compliant substrates.

Keywords: Buckling load, elastic half-plane, Timoshenko beam, frictionless contact, Chebyshev polynomials

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1. Introduction

2 The knowledge of the critical load of elastic bars, beams, plates, shell panels
and layered systems bonded to a deformable support is a key task for many
4 engineering problems with specific reference to foundation beams, bridge decks,
end-bearing piles and thin-film based devices (MEMS and NEMS) [1]. The
6 buckling problem is usually formulated as an eigenvalue problem, whose solution
provides both the buckling loads and the corresponding mode shapes.

8 In general, the mechanical interaction between an elastic beam and the un-
derlying substrate involves both shear and normal (peel) stresses [2]. However,
10 in many practical applications the shear stress is usually small and thus it can
be neglected according to the simplifying assumption of frictionless contact [3].
12 Moreover, the weight forces hinder the lifting of the beam from the substrate,
thus making reasonable the assumption of bilateral contact for a wide class of
14 practical cases.

The simplest model adopted for representing an elastic support is the Win-
16 kler foundation. In this case, the support is represented by a series of discrete
and mutually independent elastic springs that can transmit to the beam a dis-
18 tributed transverse load proportional to the deflection of the beam. The soil
stiffness is thus represented by a single substrate constant. As a consequence of
20 its simplicity, many Authors extensively used such a scheme to study the buck-
ling of beams on a deformable support [4, 5, 6]. Since its proposal, the Winkler
22 model was subjected to a strong criticism by Wieghardt [7] and many others ow-
ing to the fact that it leads to a rough approximation of the displacement field.
24 Therefore, a non-local generalization of the Winkler model was later introduced
by Wieghardt, who assumed that the contact pressure depends locally both on
26 the deflection and curvature of the beam through two distinct parameters. The
buckling problem of a beam laying on a Wieghardt foundation was investigated
28 in [8, 9].

Accurate analyses of the interaction between a beam and an underlying sub-
30 strate can be performed by simulating the substrate (if it is large enough w.r.t.

the supported element) as a 2D semi-infinite elastic medium. Such an approach
32 has been pursued by Shield et al. [10] for studying an Eulero-Bernoulli (E-B)
beam resting on an incompressible elastic half-plane subjected to a uniform re-
34 motely applied strain. These authors also accounted for a shear-type cohesive
zone at the interface in the neighbouring of the beam ends. Later, Lanzoni and
36 Radi [11] extended the analysis by considering a shear deformable Timoshenko
beam resting on an elastic and isotropic half-plane and loaded by transversal
38 forces. In this case, a complex power stress singularity is found at the beam ends,
which depends on the Poisson ratio of the half-plane. Moreover, in proximity of
40 the inner section of a Timoshenko beam loaded by a concentrated transversal
force the pressure distribution between the beam and the half-plane displays a
42 logarithmic singularity and the shear stress is finite and discontinuous across the
loaded section, whereas for the E-B beam model the pressure was found regular
44 therein. Accurate numerical studies about the interfacial stresses between bars
and beams and an elastic 2D half-plane can be found in [12], recently extended
46 to a 3D half-space [13].

The effect of a compressive load acting on an E-B beam resting on an elas-
48 tic half-plane has been investigated analytically by Gallagher [14] by using a
Chebyshev series expansion for representing the beam deflection. This Author
50 considered special boundary conditions (BCs) for the beam, which was indeed
assumed simply supported at the edges. However, the model of a continuum
52 medium cannot sustain the concentrated loads that the supports can provide.
Moreover, in most practical cases the beam is free at the edges and it may lift
54 off the substrate. By using a coupled FE-BIE formulation involving the Green
function for the half-plane, Tullini et al. [15, 16] solved the buckling problem
56 of Timoshenko beam in contact with an elastic half-plane under various BCs.
Except for the work by Gallagher concerning E-B beams, the aforementioned
58 investigations are based on numerical approaches and, to authors knowledge, a
comprehensive analytical study on the stability of a Timoshenko beam bonded
60 to an elastic half-plane cannot be found in Literature.

In the present work, the 2D problem of a compressed Timoshenko beam

62 of finite length in frictionless contact with an elastic and isotropic half-plane
is analytically investigated. Based on the relationship between the interfacial
64 pressure and the displacement according to the Green function for an elastic
half-plane loaded at its surface, the problem is found to be governed by an
66 integro-differential equation that is reduced to an algebraic system by expand-
ing the rotation of the beam cross sections in series of Chebyshev polynomials
68 of the first kind. Two dimensionless parameters denoting the relative flexural
and shear stiffnesses of the beam completely characterize the system. The
70 beam is considered free at its edges, thus requiring the vanishing of both the
bending moment and the transverse force therein. Two different kinds of beam
72 edges are considered in detail, namely sharp and smooth edges, which affect
the distribution of the peel stress within the contact region. For convenience,
74 the corresponding eigenvalue problem for even and odd modes is formulated
separately and then solved for the buckling loads. The analytical results show
76 that the edge shape has a strong influence on the buckling load. In particular,
it is shown that a beam with smooth edges cannot display a rigid-body critical
78 mode, differently from a beam with sharp edges.

The paper is organized as follows: The problem formulation and the BCs
80 are presented in Section 2. The solution is worked out in Section 3 for even
and odd buckling modes separately, whereas the main results are reported and
82 commented within Section 4. In particular, some reference cases have been
analysed in Section 4.1. The convergence rate of the series solution varying the
84 governing parameters has been also investigated therein. The buckling of a rigid
beam resting on an elastic half-plane is discussed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3 and
86 relevant differences are found between the two kinds of beam edges. Finally,
conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

88 **2. Problem formulation**

2.1. *Governing equations*

90 Let us consider a Timoshenko beam of length $2a$ in frictionless contact with an elastic half-plane and subjected at its ends to compressive axial loads P , as sketched in Figure 1. The interfacial shear stress will be neglect in the following.

Figure 1: Reference system.

92

Accounting for friction at the interface would indeed result in strongly non-linear
 94 integro-differential equations that can be solved only by numerical approaches.

The plane problem is formulated per unit depth. The beam is characterized
 96 by the Young and shear moduli E_b and G_b , the moment of inertia I_b and the shear area $\overline{A}_b = A_b/\chi$, being A_b the area of the beam cross section and χ the shear factor. The contact domain between the beam and the half-plane coincides with the full length $2a$ of the beam. The elastic half-plane is characterized
 98 by the Young modulus \overline{E}_h , being $\overline{E}_h = E_h/(1 - \nu_h^2)$ or $\overline{E}_h = E_h$ for plane strain or generalized plane stress, respectively, and ν_h is the Poisson ratio.

102 The origin of the reference system is placed at the middle-span of the beam with the x axis positive if rightward directed along the contact region, as reported in Figure 1. At the interface the beam is subjected to the peel stress $q(x)$
 104 exchanged with the underlying substrate. It is worth noticing that the effect

106 of the compressive axial forces P resembles that of a temperature variation ΔT
 according to $P = E_b h[(1 + \nu_h)\alpha_h - (1 + \nu_b)\alpha_b]\Delta T$ or $P = E_b h[\alpha_h - \alpha_b]\Delta T$ for
 108 plane strain or plane stress, respectively, where α_i represents the coefficient of
 thermal expansion and subscripts 'h' and 'b' denote relevant quantities for
 110 the half-plane and beam [17].

For the Timoshenko beam, the deflection $v(x)$ and rotation $\varphi(x)$ of the cross
 112 sections are related by the following kinematic relation

$$\varphi(x) = -v'(x) + \gamma(x), \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma(x)$ is the shear strain and the apex denotes differentiation w.r.t. the
 114 spatial variable x . The constitutive relations connecting the bending moment
 $M(x)$ and shear stress resultant $T(x)$ to the curvature $\varphi'(x)$ and shear compli-
 116 ance $\gamma(x)$ read

$$M(x) = E_b I_b \varphi'(x), \quad T(x) = G_b \bar{A}_b \gamma(x). \quad (2)$$

For convenience, the vertical stress resultant $V(x)$ acting on the beam cross
 118 section will be introduced in the following. Under the assumption of small
 deformations, the balance conditions for an infinitesimal beam element of length
 120 dx (see Figure 2) in the deformed configuration yield the following relations [4]:

$$V'(x) = -q(x), \quad T(x) = M'(x) = V(x) + P v'(x). \quad (3)$$

By combining eqns (1-3), a third-order ODE for the rotation of the beam cross

Figure 2: Free-body diagram of an infinitesimal beam element in the deformed configuration.

122 sections is found:

$$E_b I_b \left(1 - \frac{P}{G_b \overline{A_b}} \right) \varphi'''(x) + P \varphi'(x) + q(x) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The governing eqn (4) highlights the coupling between the beam and half-plane
124 thought the interfacial (peel) normal stress $q(x)$.

Two different kinds of beam edges are considered: *sharp edges* and *smooth*
126 *edges*, which induce (square-root) singular or vanishing pressure at the edges,
respectively, namely $q(\pm a) \rightarrow \infty$ or $q(\pm a) = 0$. As well known, the peeling
128 stress can be expressed as a function of the half-plane surface displacement
according to the Cauchy integral [18]

$$q(x) = \frac{\overline{E}_h}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}(x/a)} \int_{-a}^{+a} \frac{\mathcal{K}(t/a)}{t-x} v'(t) dt, \quad (5)$$

130 where

$$\mathcal{K}(t) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1-t^2}, & \text{for sharp beam edges,} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-t^2}}, & \text{for smooth beam edges,} \end{cases}$$

is termed *edges function*. By introducing the dimensionless variable $\xi = x/a$,
132 based on eqns (1) and (5), the governing eqn (4) provides the following integro-
differential equation for the rotation field $\varphi(\xi)$

$$(1 - \tilde{P}\rho)\varphi'''(\xi) + \tilde{P}\varphi'(\xi) + \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}(\xi)} \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{\mathcal{K}(s)}{s-\xi} [\rho\varphi''(s) - \varphi(s)] ds = 0, \quad (6)$$

134 where $\tilde{P} = Pa^2/E_b I_b$ is the normalized axial load and

$$\kappa = \frac{\overline{E}_h a^3}{E_b I_b}, \quad \rho = \frac{E_b I_b}{a^2 G_b \overline{A_b}}, \quad (7)$$

are two dimensionless parameters denoting the flexural compliance of the beam
136 as compared to that of the half-plane and the ratio between the bending and
shear stiffnesses of the beam, respectively. In the following, κ and ρ will be
138 called *stiffness parameter* and *shear parameter*, respectively.

The beam edges are assumed as free. Accordingly, the BCs demand the
140 vanishing of both the bending moment M and vertical force V therein, namely,

by using eqns (2) and (3)

$$\varphi' = 0, \quad (1 - \tilde{P}\rho)\varphi'' + \tilde{P}\varphi = 0, \quad \text{for } \xi = \pm 1. \quad (8)$$

142 **3. Problem solution**

3.1. Solution strategy

144 The problem is approached by expanding the second derivative of the ro-
 146 tation field $\varphi''(\xi)$ in series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind $T_n(\xi)$.
 148 Once the integral in the pressure term has been evaluated in closed form, the
 governing equation is transformed into an infinite series of Chebyshev poly-
 nomials with unknown coefficients C_n . Then the Galerkin procedure is applied by
 multiplying both sides of equation by a set of appropriate functions and then
 150 integrating along the contact domain. In this way, by truncating the series at
 the N^{th} term, an algebraic system for the coefficients of the series expansion is
 152 obtained and solved by using a suitable normalization condition. This allows
 providing the buckling modes up to an arbitrary amplitude constant. For con-
 154 venience, in the following the procedure is illustrated for even and odds modes,
 separately.

156 3.2. Even modes

In order to account for the even modes, the second order derivative of the
 158 rotation field is expanded in series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind,
 $T_n(\xi)$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\varphi''(\xi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} T_{2n-1}(\xi), \quad (9)$$

160 where C_{2n-1} are the unknown coefficients. Higher and lower order derivatives
 of eqn (9) can be easily obtained by using relations (31-33) provided in the
 162 Appendix 6.1. Hence, the rotation field and its derivatives involved in the
 governing eqn (6) can be written in terms of Chebyshev polynomials of the first

164 and second kinds

$$\varphi'''(\xi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (2n-1)C_{2n-1}U_{2n-2}(\xi), \quad (10)$$

$$\varphi'(\xi) = \chi_0 + \frac{C_1}{4}T_2(\xi) + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} \left[\frac{T_{2n}(\xi)}{n} - \frac{T_{2n-2}(\xi)}{n-1} \right], \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\xi) = & \chi_0 T_1(\xi) + \frac{C_1}{24} [T_3(\xi) - 3T_1(\xi)] + \frac{C_3}{80} [10T_1(\xi) - 5T_3(\xi) + T_5(\xi)] \\ & + \frac{1}{8} \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{C_{2n-1}}{n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3]} [n(2n+1)T_{2n-3}(\xi) \\ & + (2n+1)(3-2n)T_{2n-1}(\xi) + (n-1)(2n-3)T_{2n+1}(\xi)], \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

where χ_0 is an integration constant.

166 Due to the assumed symmetry properties, it is sufficient to impose the BCs
 (8) at one edge only. Relations (8) are thus used to obtain the constant χ_0 and
 168 the coefficient C_3 in terms of the other unknown coefficients, namely

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_0 &= \frac{1}{4} \left[-C_1 + \frac{C_3}{2} + \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{C_{2n-1}}{(n-1)n} \right], \\ C_3 &= C_1 \frac{5}{3} \frac{\tilde{P}(3\rho+1) - 3}{\tilde{P}(1-5\rho) + 5} + 5 \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} \frac{\tilde{P} \left[\frac{1}{3-4(n-1)n} + \rho \right] - 1}{\tilde{P}(1-5\rho) + 5}. \end{aligned}$$

The introduction of the series expansions (9) and (12) into the peel stress dis-
 170 tribution (5) provides

$$q(\xi) = \frac{\bar{E}_h}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}(\xi)} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq 2}}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{\mathcal{K}(s)}{s-\xi} q_{2n-1}(s) ds, \quad (13)$$

where functions $q_{2n-1}(s)$ for $n = 1, 3, 4, \dots, \infty$ are listed in Appendix 6.2. De-
 172 pending on the edges function $\mathcal{K}(s)$, relations (34) and (35) for smooth or sharp
 edges are used to evaluate in closed form the integral in expression (13) (for
 174 details see Appendix 6.2). As a consequence, the governing equation (6) trans-
 forms into an infinite series of Chebyshev polynomials with unknown coefficients
 176 C_{2n-1} for $n = 1, 3, 4, \dots, \infty$

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq 2}}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} f_{2n-1}(\xi) = 0, \quad (14)$$

where functions $f_{2n-1}(\xi)$ for $n = 1, 3, 4, \dots, \infty$ are defined in Appendix 6.2.
 178 Such functions are linear combinations of Chebyshev polynomials and depend
 on the dimensionless axial load \tilde{P} and governing parameters ρ and κ .

180 In order to solve the governing equation (14) for the unknown coefficients,
 eqn (14) is now multiplied by $T_m(\xi)/\sqrt{1-\xi^2}$ or $T_m(\xi)$, with $m = 1, 3, \dots$, for
 182 smooth or sharp edges, respectively, and then integrated for ξ ranging between
 -1 and 1 . Therefore, the following infinite eigen-system is derived in closed
 184 form

$$\mathbf{A}(\tilde{P})\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{c} is the vector collecting the unknown coefficients and $\mathbf{A}(\tilde{P})$ is the matrix
 186 defined in Appendix 6.2. Then, the characteristic equation of the system (15)
 reads

$$\det[\mathbf{A}(\tilde{P})] = 0, \quad (16)$$

188 which provides the eigenvalues \tilde{P}_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$. Once the eigenvalues are
 found from eqn (16), the coefficients C_{2n-1} normalized w.r.t. the first coefficient
 190 C_1 are achieved. The displacement field follows by integrating relation (1) and
 the integration constant is found by imposing $v(\pm 1) = w(\pm 1, 0) = 0$, where
 192 $w(x, 0)$ is the vertical displacement of the half-plane surface loaded by the load
 distribution (13), namely [18]

$$w(x, 0) = -2a \frac{1 - \nu_h^2}{\pi E_h} \int_{-1}^{+1} q(\xi) \ln|\xi - x| d\xi. \quad (17)$$

194 3.3. Odd modes

As for even modes, the odd modes are investigated by assuming a series ex-
 196 pansion of even Chebyshev polynomials to represent the second order derivative
 of the rotation field as

$$\varphi''(\xi) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_{2n} T_{2n}(\xi). \quad (18)$$

198 Relations (31) and (32) in Appendix A provide the derivatives of function $\varphi(\xi)$ up to the third order

$$\varphi'''(\xi) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_{2n} U_{2n-1}(\xi), \quad (19)$$

$$\varphi'(\xi) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_{2n}}{2} \left[\frac{T_{2n-1}(\xi)}{1-2n} + \frac{T_{2n+1}(\xi)}{2n+1} \right], \quad (20)$$

$$\varphi(\xi) = \varphi_0 + \frac{1}{24} \left\{ 6C_0 T_2(\xi) - \frac{C_2}{2} [8T_2(\xi) + T_4(\xi)] + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C_{2n} \left[\frac{3T_{2n-2}(\xi)}{2n^2-3n+1} + \frac{3T_{2n+2}(\xi)}{2n^2+3n+1} - \frac{6T_{2n}(\xi)}{n(4n^2-1)} \right] \right\}. \quad (21)$$

200 By imposing the BCs (8), the rigid rotation φ_0 and coefficient C_2 can be written as functions of the unknown coefficients C_{2n} for $n = 0, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$, namely

$$\varphi_0 = 3 \left(C_0 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{C_{2n}}{1-4n^2} \right),$$

$$C_2 = C_0 \frac{\tilde{P}(64\rho+3) - 64}{16\tilde{P}} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C_{2n} \frac{64 + \tilde{P}[5 - 64(n^2-1)^2\rho] + n^2[64(n^2-2) + 7\tilde{P}]}{16(4n^4 - 5n^2 + 1)\tilde{P}}.$$

202 Due to relations (18) and (21), the load term (5) becomes

$$q(\xi) = \frac{\bar{E}_h}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}(\xi)} \sum_{\substack{n=0 \\ n \neq 1}}^{\infty} C_{2n} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{\mathcal{K}(s)}{s-\xi} q_{2n}(\xi) ds, \quad (22)$$

where functions $q_{2n}(\xi)$ for $n = 0, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$ are listed in Appendix 6.2. Therefore, the governing equation (6) assumes the form of an infinite series of Chebyshev polynomials involving the unknown coefficients C_{2n} for $n = 0, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$,
204 as
206 as

$$\sum_{\substack{n=0 \\ n \neq 1}}^{\infty} C_{2n} f_{2n}(\xi) = 0. \quad (23)$$

where functions $f_{2n}(\xi)$ for $n = 0, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$ are reported in Appendix 6.2.

208 The solution is achieved by following the same procedure used for the even modes. Matrix $\mathbf{A}(\tilde{P})$ and vector \mathbf{c} collecting the coefficients of the Chebyshev polynomials for the odd modes are reported in Appendix 6.2.

Then, the eigenvalues \tilde{P}_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$ are determined as the roots of the characteristic equation (16) and the corresponding eigenvectors \mathbf{c}_i are obtained from the non-trivial solution of the homogeneous eigensystem (15) by
212

214 introducing a suitable normalization w.r.t. the coefficient C_0 . Finally, the inte-
 216 gration constant corresponding to a rigid body motion is assessed by requiring
 $v(0) = 0$, according to the skew-symmetry condition of the odd modes.

4. Results and discussion

218 The eigenvalues determined by solving the characteristic eqn (16) both for
 odd and even modes and for sharp and smooth beam edges are presented and
 220 discussed in the present section by varying the governing parameters of the
 system. Attention is paid to the series expansions convergence. The edge effects
 222 on the buckling loads and mode shapes are investigated in detail.

Five reference cases have been considered, whose governing parameters are
 reported in Table 1. In order to validate the results provided by the present

Case	$\rho = \frac{E_b I_b}{G_b A_b a^2}$	$\kappa = \frac{\bar{E}_b a^3}{E_b I_b}$
1	0	15.625
2	0	1953
3	0.032	15.625
4	0.0036	1953
5	0	0.125

Table 1: Reference cases: dimensionless governing parameters.

224 study, ρ and κ for cases 1 to 4 have been set in order to reproduce the study
 cases reported in [15, 16]. To be specific, ρ and κ are related to the governing
 226 parameters αL and h/L used in [15, 16] by

$$\kappa = (\alpha L)^{\frac{3}{8}}, \quad \rho = \frac{4h}{5L}, \quad \text{with } L = 2a. \quad (24)$$

228 Cases 1 and 2 are representative of an E-B beam resting on a compliant and
 stiff half-plane, respectively, whereas cases 3 and 4 simulate a Timoshenko beam
 230 on a soft and stiff elastic half-plane, respectively. The last case 5 corresponds
 to an E-B beam resting on a very compliant support. In this limit case, the

232 beam is expected to buckle as a free beam, namely the first buckling load is
 almost vanishing and the corresponding buckling mode resembles a rigid body
 234 rotation. In the following, subscripts s_h and s_m denote a beam with sharp and
 smooth edges, respectively.

236 The results are reported in terms of the normalized buckling loads

$$p_i = \frac{P_i}{P_E} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \tilde{P}_i,$$

namely the i -th buckling load P_i is normalized w.r.t. the Euler critical load
 238 $P_{cr,E} = \pi^2 E_b I_b / 4a^2$ of a simply supported beam.

In the following, $\Pi_i = P_{i,s_h} / P_{i,s_m}$ will be defined as *edge effect parameter*,
 240 being the ratio between the eigenvalues obtained for a beam with sharp and
 smooth edges corresponding to the same mode number i .

242 4.1. Buckling loads and modes

The normalized eigenvalues p_i , for $i = 1 \div 4$, are reported in Tables (2-5) for
 244 cases 1 to 4. Symbol \sim denotes the convergence achievement. To be specific,
 we assume that the convergence is attained when the relative error between the
 246 solution obtained with N terms and that obtained with $N + 1$ terms is lower
 than 0.1%.

Sharp edges			Smooth edges					
Mode	Present Analysis		[16]	Mode	Series terms			Edges effect
	Series terms, N				4	10	12	
1 ^(e)	2.002	~	2.002	1 ^(e)	3.492	3.754	3.728	0.53
2 ^(o)	2.321	~	2.369	2 ^(o)	5.137	~	~	0.45
3 ^(o)	5.023	~	5.021	3 ^(e)	16.155	9.791	9.773	0.51
4 ^(e)	9.596	~	9.594	4 ^(o)	18.705	16.540	~	0.58

Table 2: Case 1 ($\rho = 0$, $\kappa = 15.625$): dimensionless eigenvalues p_i and edges effect $\Pi_i = P_{i,s_h} / P_{i,s_m}$. Symbols ^(o) and ^(e) denote odd and even modes respectively.

Sharp edges				Smooth edges			
Mode	Present Analysis		[16]	Mode	Series terms		Edges effect
	Series terms, N				10	12	Π
	5	10					
$1^{(e)}$	52.426	52.112	52.056	$1^{(e)}$	77.138	77.183	0.67
$2^{(o)}$	52.172	\sim	52.117	$2^{(o)}$	78.324	\sim	0.66
$3^{(o)}$	78.167	\sim	78.168	$3^{(o)}$	83.340	83.913	0.93
$4^{(e)}$	80.606	79.513	79.511	$4^{(e)}$	85.839	85.911	0.93

Table 3: Case 2 ($\rho = 0$, $\kappa = 1953.13$): dimensionless eigenvalues p_i and edges effect $\Pi_i = P_{i,Sh}/P_{i,Sm}$. Symbols $^{(o)}$ and $^{(e)}$ denote odd and even modes respectively.

Sharp edges				Smooth edges				
Mode	Present Analysis		[15]	Mode	Series terms		Edges effect	
	Series terms, N				4	10	12	Π
	4	5						
$1^{(e)}$	1.918	\sim	1.917	$1^{(e)}$	3.300	3.664	\sim	0.52
$2^{(o)}$	2.225	\sim	2.224	$2^{(o)}$	4.175	\sim	\sim	0.53
$3^{(o)}$	4.147	\sim	4.147	$3^{(e)}$	7.913	6.077	6.051	0.68
$4^{(e)}$	5.863	\sim	5.864	$4^{(o)}$	7.999	7.609	\sim	0.77

Table 4: Case 3 ($\rho = 0.032$, $\kappa = 15.625$): dimensionless eigenvalues p_i and edges effect $\Pi_i = P_{i,Sh}/P_{i,Sm}$. Symbols $^{(o)}$ and $^{(e)}$ denote odd and even modes respectively.

248 The convergence rate is influenced by the nature of the beam edges, the
mode shape and the governing parameters. In particular, the convergence rate
250 is faster for sharp edges than for smooth edges. Indeed, in case of smooth
edges, a large number of terms is required for addressing the convergence, with
252 the exception of the first odd mode, as shown in Tables (2-5). In addition, the
convergence rate decreases as κ and ρ increase, specially for even modes.

254 Tables 2 and 4 show that the eigenvalues decrease as the shear parameter

Sharp edges				Smooth edges			
Mode	Present Analysis		[15]	Mode	Series terms		Edges effect
	Series terms, N				10	12	Π
	5	10					
$1^{(e)}$	46.770	46.362	46.342	$1^{(o)}$	70.181	\sim	0.66
$2^{(o)}$	46.416	\sim	46.399	$2^{(e)}$	70.267	70.439	0.66
$3^{(e)}$	72.839	70.400	70.400	$3^{(e)}$	72.068	73.705	0.95
$4^{(o)}$	70.776	\sim	70.776	$4^{(o)}$	73.134	\sim	0.96

Table 5: Case 4 ($\rho = 0.0036$, $\kappa = 1953.13$): dimensionless eigenvalues p_i and edges effect $\Pi_i = P_{i,Sh}/P_{i,Sm}$. Symbols $^{(o)}$ and $^{(e)}$ denote odd and even modes respectively.

ρ increases, as well as the stiffness parameter κ decreases. For small values of the parameter κ , the shear compliance of the beam has no significant effects on the buckling load and mode. Indeed, in this case the buckling mode resembles a rigid body motion.

Conversely, the edges shape significantly affects the buckling loads, as shown in Tables (2-5) concerning the first 4 modes for cases 1 \div 4, particularly for low values of κ (stiff beams on compliant substrates), with special reference to the first mode shape. The order in which the mode shape occurs (symmetric or skew) is also influenced by the edges shape. In particular, it can be observed from Tables (2-5) that only case 2 exhibits the same sorting (alternated even and odd modes) both for sharp and smooth edges (symbols $^{(o)}$ or $^{(e)}$ denote odd or even modes, respectively). In all the other cases the mode sorting changes according to the kind of the beam edges.

The effects induced by the governing parameters are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, where the dimensionless buckling loads are plotted varying κ and ρ , respectively, for the considered reference cases. Even and odd modes are plotted in solid and dashed lines, respectively, whereas red and blue lines refer to beams with sharp and smooth edges, respectively. Vertical black lines denote the reference cases considered in Table 1. The results are plotted in Figs. 3-4(c-d) for $\kappa \leq 2000$

Figure 3: Dimensionless buckling loads varying the relative soil stiffness $\kappa = \bar{E}_h a^3 / E_b I_b$: even modes (continuous lines) and odd modes (dashed lines). The red background highlights the $\kappa < \kappa_1$ region. (a) Beams with sharp edges: $\rho = 0.032$, low κ values; (b) Beams with smooth edges: $\rho = 0.032$, low κ values; (c) Beams with sharp edges: $\rho = 0.0036$, high κ values; (d) Beams with smooth edges: $\rho = 0.0036$, high κ values.

274 and $\rho \leq 0.04$, respectively.

275 By comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(c) for beams with sharp edges, with Figs. 3(c)
 276 and 3(d) concerning beams with smooth edges, a switch between even and odd
 modes is observed. Moreover, as already noticed by Gallagher [14], the curves
 278 never intersect each others. In particular, both for odd or even modes, the curves

Figure 4: Dimensionless buckling loads varying the shear parameter $\rho = E_b I_b / a^2 G_b \bar{A}_b$: even modes (continuous lines) and odd modes (dashed lines). (a) Beams with sharp edges: $\kappa = 1953$, low ρ values; (b) Beams with smooth edges: $\kappa = 1953$, low ρ values; (c) Beams with sharp edges: $\kappa = 15.625$, high ρ values; (d) Beams with smooth edges: $\kappa = 15.625$, high ρ values.

280 behave smoothly everywhere except where they approached each other. Therein,
 instead of continuing smoothly and crossing, they suddenly deviate and do not
 intersect. Such a behavior is known as *veering* phenomenon [19]. Conversely,
 282 curves related to odd modes may intersect those representing even modes and
 viceversa. In this case, the intersection points denote the simultaneous occurring

284 of even and odd modes under the same buckling load. The values of κ in
correspondence of which the buckling loads of the first even mode coincide with
286 those of the first odd mode will be denoted as κ_i . In particular, for a given value
of the shear compliance ρ , the smallest value of κ for which the switch between
288 the first odd mode and the first even mode occurs will be denoted by κ_1 .

Making reference to case 3, for beams with sharp edges we found $\kappa_1 \cong 11.53$,
290 as shown in Fig. 3(a). Therefore, for $\kappa < \kappa_1$ (compliant half-plane) the first
buckling mode is odd and close to a rigid rotation, whereas for $\kappa_1 < \kappa < \kappa_2$
292 the first buckling mode is even. Note also that for beams with smooth edges we
obtained $\kappa_1 \cong 10.12$.

294 The buckling loads varying the shear parameter ρ are reported in Figs. 4(a)-
4(d). For low values of ρ and high value of κ the veering phenomenon can be
296 observed both for beams with sharp and smooth edges, as shown in Figs.4(a)
and 4(b), respectively. As the parameter ρ grows, the buckling loads and modes
298 tend to approach each others, with special reference to higher modes, as shown
in Figs.4(c) and 4(d). Note also that the lowest even and odd modes are almost
300 unaffected by the parameter ρ , as confirmed by the results listed in Tables 2-5.

The buckling modes and loads of beams with sharp edges are represented in
302 Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b), respectively, varying both the parameters ρ and κ .
In particular, grey regions in Figure 5(a) identify the occurrence of odd modes
304 corresponding to the first critical load $P_1^{(o)}$. Conversely, white regions denote
the occurrence of even modes. The zoom in Figure 5(a) allows assessing that
306 for $\rho < 0.1$, which is relevant for practical cases, the first mode is always odd
provided that $\kappa < 10$.

308 The dimensionless buckling loads corresponding to the first six modes for the
considered study cases are reported in detail in Fig. 6. In particular, Figs. 6(c)
310 and 6(d) show that the buckling modes of beams with smooth edges involve
larger wave number and higher buckling loads than for beams with sharp edges.
312 Therefore, Fig. 6 together with the quantities $\Pi_i = P_{i,Sh}/P_{i,Sm}$ provided in
Tables (2-5) show that beams with smooth edges display higher buckling loads
314 w.r.t. beams with sharp edges. Indeed, the edge effect parameter ranges between

Figure 5: First critical modes and corresponding buckling loads. (a) Nature of the first critical modes. Grey regions identify the occurrence of odd modes, white regions denote even modes; (b) Dimensionless first critical loads varying the governing parameters κ and ρ .

0.5 $\leq \Pi \leq 1$ and the curves denoting the buckling loads of beams with smooth edges lay over those of beams with sharp edges for all the reference cases. Such a difference is more evident for cases 1 and 3 and for the first modes, for which a beam with smooth edges exhibits a critical load almost double of that of a beam with sharp edges.

A rigid-body like buckling mode does not occur for beams with smooth edges resting on a compliant half-plane (see Figure 6(e)). Conversely, Figure 6(c) shows that beams with sharp edges exhibit a first odd buckling mode close to a rigid rotation. Note also that when the stiffness of the half-plane is low (cases 1, 5), the buckling loads approach those of a simply supported E-B beam, namely $p_i \approx n^2$. Such a trend is not observed for case 3, despite the compliance of the half-plane. This is due to the fact that case 3 is characterized by a very high shear compliance of the beam ($\rho = 0.032$). For such a situation it is worth noticing that the buckling loads of beams with sharp and smooth edges tend to coincide as the mode number increases, accordingly to Figure 4.

4.2. Rigid beam resting on a compliant half-plane

The first buckling load of a rigid beam resting on a compliant substrate, namely as $\kappa \rightarrow 0^+$, is investigated in the present Section.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 6: Dimensionless buckling loads and associated buckling modes. (a) Case 1; (b) Case 2; (c) Case 3; (d) Case 4; (e) Case 5 (vanishing half-plane).

Looking for the solution of the governing eqn (6) as a constant term ϕ_0 , the
 334 only non-vanishing term turns out to be the load contribution (5) whatever the
 edge function $\mathcal{K}(t)$ ¹, namely

$$q(\xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{\bar{E}_h \phi_0}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{\sqrt{1-s^2}}{s-\xi} U_0(s) ds, & \text{for sharp edges,} \\ \frac{\bar{E}_h \phi_0}{2\pi} \sqrt{1-\xi^2} \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{T_0(s)}{(s-\xi)\sqrt{1-s^2}} ds, & \text{for smooth edges.} \end{cases}$$

336 However, by using eqn (34) the pressure distribution for beams with smooth
 edges is zero. Therefore, the moment generated by the axial loads P as a
 338 consequence of a rigid rotation ϕ_0 of the beam, namely

$$M_0 = 2\phi_0 Pa, \quad (25)$$

cannot be balanced by the soil reaction, except for $P = 0$, namely for the trivial
 340 solution. Therefore, a rigid-like buckling mode cannot occur for beams with
 smooth edges.

342 Conversely, the peel stress distribution at the beam ends is singular for beams
 with sharp edges and, based on identity (35), it reads

$$q_{sh}(\xi) = -\frac{\bar{E}_h \phi_0}{2} \frac{\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}. \quad (26)$$

344 Therefore, a square-root singular pressure takes place at the beam sharp edges
 and it can balance the external moment originated by the axial load P as a con-
 346 sequence of the rigid rotation ϕ_0 of the beam. A sketch of such a configuration
 is found in Figure 7, where the dashed line denotes the singular pressure distri-
 348 bution (26) whereas the solid line represents the pressure distribution obtained
 for case 5. Both solutions have been normalized by $\phi_0 \bar{E}_h / 2$.

350 On the other hand, the overall moment generated by the load distribution
 (26) turns out to be

$$M_0 = 2a^2 \int_0^1 q(\xi) \xi d\xi = \frac{\pi \bar{E}_h \phi_0 a^2}{4}. \quad (27)$$

¹The identities $T_0(\xi) = U_0(\xi) = 1$ are used.

Figure 7: Case 5: First mode pressure distribution. Series solution (solid line) vs closed form solution (dashed line).

352 Therefore, by comparing eqns (25) and (27) the following relation between the overall moment and the rigid rotation is found

$$\phi_0 = \frac{4M_0}{\bar{E}_h \pi a^2},$$

354 in agreement with the well known Galin solution for a rigid flat punch resting on an elastic half-plane and subject to a couple M_0 [20] .

356 A useful design formula for the first buckling load, which holds for small values of κ , is provided by comparing (25) with (27), namely

$$P_{cr}^{(o)} \approx \frac{\bar{E}_h a \pi}{8} \text{ or } p_{cr}^{(o)} \approx \frac{\kappa}{2\pi}, \quad \text{for } \kappa < \kappa_1. \quad (28)$$

358 In particular, for case 5 ($\kappa = 0.125$), the design formula (28) provides a buckling load $p_{cr}^{(o)} = 0.198$, with a relative error lower than 0.34% w.r.t. the analytical solution. Therefore, eqn (28) can be used to predict the buckling loads of rigid beams resting on compliant substrates.

362 4.3. Beam resting on a Winkler foundation

The dimensionless buckling loads of an E-B beam resting on a Winkler foundation (WF) are reported in Figure 8(a) varying the dimensionless parameter $\tilde{k} = \kappa a^4 / E_b I_b$, being k the subgrade constant [6]. As expected, for $k \rightarrow 0^+$ the critical loads resemble those of a simply supported E-B beam ($p_i \approx n^2$). It is worth noticing that, similarly to the case of beams resting on a half-plane,

368 the veering phenomenon occurs also for beams resting on a local foundation.
 Other similarities occur w.r.t. Figure 3 concerning beams resting on an elastic
 370 half-plane, with specific reference to Figures 3(c)-3(d) related to beams having
 a vanishing shear compliance ρ . In particular, the trend of curves in Figure 8(a)
 372 is close to that displayed in Figure 3(c) concerning beams with sharp edges,
 both in terms of buckling loads and sorting of even-odd modes. This analogy is
 374 confirmed by Figure 8(b), where the curves of Figure 8(a) have been represented
 together with those obtained for an E-B beam ($\rho = 0$) bonded to an elastic half-
 376 plane. Note that for compliant substrates the slope of the curves representing
 beams with smooth edges on an elastic half-plane is always greater than that
 378 of beams with sharp edges which, in turn, is greater than that of beams sup-
 ported by a WF. Therefore it seems that beams supported by a WF subjected
 380 to buckling exhibit a softer behavior w.r.t. beams on non-local foundations.
 However it should be remarked that the governing parameter \tilde{k} differs from the
 382 stiffness parameter κ of a beam bonded to an elastic half-plane. Nonetheless, a
 relationship between \tilde{k} and κ can be obtained based on some assumptions about
 384 the stiffness of the beam.

Figure 8: (a) Dimensionless buckling loads of an E-B beam resting on a Winkler foundation
 varying the parameter $\tilde{k} = ka^4/E_b I_b$; (b) Critical loads of an E-B beam supported by the
 Winkler foundation compared with those of an E-B beam resting on an elastic half-plane.

As an example, for rigid beams resting on compliant substrates, in particular
 386 for $\kappa < \kappa_1$, a straightforward relation can be established between the stiffness of
 a WF and the elastic modulus of a half-plane. Let us consider a flat punch on a
 388 WF subjected to a rotation ϕ_0 around its centre. Then, the interfacial pressure
 distribution assumes the form

$$q_{WF}(\xi) = -k\phi_0\xi a,$$

390 which implies an external moment M_0 given by

$$M_0 = \frac{2}{3}k\phi_0a^3. \quad (29)$$

Therefore, by comparing eqn (27) and (29), the following relation between
 392 \bar{E}_h and the subgrade constant k of the WF holds

$$k = \frac{3\bar{E}_h}{8a}\pi, \quad \text{or} \quad \tilde{k} = \frac{3}{8}\pi\kappa. \quad (30)$$

Therefore, the buckling load of a rigid beam on a WF can be obtained from
 (28) where κ is derived by (30) in terms of Winkler constant k . Fig. 9(a) shows

Figure 9: (a) Dimensionless buckling loads p_{cr} predicted by eqn (28) compared with the buckling loads of beams with sharp edges resting on a half-plane (HP) and on Winkler foundation (WF) for different values of ρ ; (b) relative errors $\epsilon_r = 1 - P_1/P_{cr}^{(o)}$ between formula (28) and the exact solution varying the parameter κ .

394

the buckling loads provided by relation (28) (green lines) and those obtained
 396 for beams (with sharp edges) resting on a half-plane varying κ for some values
 of ρ . The relative errors are shown in Fig. 9(b).

398 As expected, formula (28) predicts reasonably well the first bulking load for
low values of κ , as shown in Fig.9(a). The discrepancy between formula (28)
400 and the effective first buckling load increases as κ and ρ increase. However,
Fig.9(b) shows that for $\kappa < 12$, the relative error is lower than 20%, also for
402 very high values of the shear compliance ρ . An alternative relation between the
subgrade constant k and the elastic modulus \bar{E}_h of the half plane can be found,
404 for example, in [21].

5. Conclusion

406 The buckling analysis of a compressed Timoshenko beam with sharp or
smooth edges in frictionless contact with an elastic half-plane has been investi-
408 gated analytically. By expanding the rotation field of the beam cross sections
in series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, the governing integro-
410 differential equation transforms into an algebraic eigenvalue problem which is
solved for the unknown coefficients involved in the series expansion. This ap-
412 proach allowed assessing both the buckling loads and mode shapes varying the
governing parameters ρ and κ which involves the flexural and shear compliance
414 of the beam, respectively. Five study cases have been investigated in detail, and
the obtained results have been compared with those available in the Literature,
416 founding good agreement.

The influence of the stiffness parameter κ on the buckling load is more
418 pronounced than that of the shear parameter ρ . Moreover, the dependence
of the buckling loads on the shear compliance is more evident for higher modes.
420 It is worth noticing that parameter κ affects also the sorting of the (even or
odd) modes corresponding to the critical loads.

422 It has been shown that beams with smooth edges cannot exhibit rigid-body
like modes. Conversely, for beams with sharp edges a particular value of the
424 parameter κ , called κ_1 , has been interpreted as a soil stiffness threshold for the
occurrence of a rigid-like mode. Indeed, for $\kappa < \kappa_1$ the first buckling mode of
426 the system is odd and it resembles a rigid body rotation. On the other hand

it has been shown that for $\rho < 0.1$, the first mode exhibited by stiff beams on
428 compliant supports (i.e. $\kappa < 9$) is always odd. A simple relation to predict the
buckling loads of beams on compliant substrate has been proposed also.

430 Based on the Galin solution for the rigid punch, a straightforward relation-
ship between the subgrade constant of the Winkler foundation and the elastic
432 constants of the half-plane holding for rigid beams has been found.

The performed results can be used as a reliable support for the design of
434 layered systems characterized by high length-to-thickness ratios, for which the
instability phenomena represent the main task. The challenging problem of a
436 compressed beam in frictional contact with an underlying elastic support will
be handled in a future work.

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502 6. Appendix

6.1. Integrals involving Chebyshev polynomials

504 The following relations [22] involving the Chebyshev polynomials have been
used:

$$T'_n(\xi) = n U_{n-1}(\xi) \quad (31)$$

$$\int T_n(x) dx = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{T_{n+1}(x)}{n+1} - \frac{T_{|n-1|}(x)}{n-1} \right], & n \neq 1 \\ \frac{1}{4} T_2(x), & n = 1 \end{cases}, \quad (32)$$

$$T_n(\xi) = \frac{1}{2} [U_n(\xi) - U_{n-2}(\xi)] \quad (33)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{T_n(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(x-y)} dx = \text{sign}(n) \pi U_{n-1}(y), \quad (34)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sqrt{1-x^2} U_n(x)}{x-y} dx = \begin{cases} \pi T_{n+1}(y), & \text{for } n \leq -2 \\ -\pi T_{n+1}(y), & \text{for } n > -2, \\ 0, & n = -1 \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{U_n(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}(x-y)} dx = \begin{cases} 2\pi \sum_{j=1,3,\dots}^n U_{j-1}(y), & \text{for } n \text{ odd} \\ 2\pi \sum_{j=2,4,\dots}^n U_{j-1}(y), & \text{for } n \text{ even} \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\sqrt{1-x^2} T_n(x)}{x-y} dx = \frac{\pi}{2} [T_{n-1}(y) - T_{n+1}(y)]. \quad (37)$$

Integral terms,

$$t_{n,m} = \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{T_n(\xi)T_m(\xi)}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} d\xi = \begin{cases} \pi/2, & \text{if } n = m \neq 0, \\ \pi, & \text{if } n = m = 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } n \neq m \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

$$l_{n,m} = \int_{-1}^{+1} T_n(x)T_m(x) dx = r_{n,m} = \begin{cases} \frac{(1-m^2-n^2)[(-1)^{m+n}+1]}{-2(m^2+1)n^2+(m^2-1)^2+n^4} & , \text{ if } n+m \text{ even} \\ 0 & \text{other cases} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

$$r_{n,m} = \int_{-1}^{+1} U_{n-1}(x)T_m(x) dx = \begin{cases} \frac{2n}{n^2-m^2}, & \text{if } n+m \text{ odd} \\ 0, & \text{if } n+m \text{ even} \end{cases}, \quad (40)$$

$$g_{n,m} = \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{U_n(x)T_m(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n+m \text{ odd or } m > n \\ \pi & \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

6.2. Problem known function and coefficient matrices

Due to the series expansion of the rotation fields and its derivatives, the load term in the governing eqn (6) can be decomposed in two parts. These two parts have been considered as the coefficients of the first Chebyshev series amplitude, and of the remaining n -dependent terms, namely,

$$q(\xi) = \frac{\bar{E}_h}{2\pi} \frac{1}{\mathcal{K}(\xi)} \int_{-1}^{+1} \frac{\mathcal{K}(s)}{s-\xi} \begin{cases} \sum_{n=1, n \neq 2}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} q_{2n-1}(s) ds, & \text{even modes} \\ \sum_{n=0, n \neq 1}^{\infty} C_{2n} q_{2n}(s) ds, & \text{odd modes} \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

512 where the functions $q_i(s)$ are defined by:

$$\begin{aligned}
q_1(s) &= T_1(s) \left[\frac{2\tilde{P}}{15\tilde{P}\rho - 3(\tilde{P} + 5)} + \rho + \frac{5}{8} \right] + T_3(s) \left[\frac{21\tilde{P} + 80}{30(-5\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} + 5)} - \rho - \frac{51}{80} \right] \\
&\quad + T_5(s) \left[\frac{\tilde{P}}{30(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} + \frac{1}{80} \right], \\
q_{2n-1}(s) &= \frac{1}{16n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3][\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \left\{ T_1(s) \left[4(5(2n-3)(2n+1)((n-1)n-1)\tilde{P}\rho \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - (n-1)n(20(n-1)n + \tilde{P} - 35) - 3(\tilde{P} + 5) \right] \right. \\
&\quad + T_3(s) \left[-5(n-1)n(16\rho + 1)(4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - 3\tilde{P}\rho - \tilde{P} + 3) \right] \\
&\quad + T_5(s) \left[(n-1)n(4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - \tilde{P}(3\rho + 1) + 3) \right] \\
&\quad + T_{2n-3}(s) \left[-2n(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5) \right] \\
&\quad + T_{2n-1}(s) \left[2(2n-3)(2n+1)(8(n-1)n\rho + 1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5) \right] \\
&\quad \left. + T_{2n+1}(s) \left[-2(n-1)(2n-3)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5) \right] \right\}, \\
q_0(s) &= \frac{T_0(s)[64 - 3\tilde{P}(16\rho + 1)] + 4T_2(s)(12\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P}) - \tilde{P}T_4(s)}{16\tilde{P}}, \\
q_{2n}(s) &= \frac{1}{16(4n^4 - 5n^2 + 1)\tilde{P}} \left\{ T_0(s) \left[-64(n^2 - 1)^2\tilde{P}\rho + n^2 \left[64(n^2 - 2) + 7\tilde{P} \right] + 5\tilde{P} + 64 \right] \right. \\
&\quad + (n+1)\tilde{P} \left[(n-1)(8(8n^2\rho - 2\rho + 1)T_{2n}(s) - 8(6\rho + 1)T_2(s) + T_4(s)) \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - 2(2n+1)T_{2n-2}(s) \right] - 2(n-1)(2n-1)\tilde{P}T_{2n+2}(s) \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Once the integral in the pressure contribute has been expanded in series of
514 Chebyshev polynomials, it can be evaluated in closed form by using relations
(34) and (35). As a results, the governing eqn is derived as,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq 2}}^{\infty} C_{2n-1} f_{2n-1}(\xi) &= 0, \quad \text{for even modes} \\
\sum_{\substack{n=0 \\ n \neq 1}}^{\infty} C_{2n} f_{2n}(\xi) &= 0, \quad \text{for odd modes}
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

516 where the functions $f_1(\xi)$ and $f_{2n-1}(\xi)$ assume different expressions for sharp or smooth edges, namely

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(\xi) &= T_0(\xi) \left\{ \tilde{P} \left[\frac{19\tilde{P}}{75\tilde{P}\rho - 15(\tilde{P} + 5)} + 2\rho + \frac{49}{40} \right] - 2 \right\} \\
&+ T_2(\xi) \frac{\kappa \frac{5(96\rho+35) - \tilde{P}[3\rho(160\rho+69)+5]}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} + 32\tilde{P}[15\tilde{P}\rho(12\rho+5) + \tilde{P} - 15(24\rho+5)] + 5760}{192[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \\
&+ T_4(\xi) \frac{\kappa \frac{3\tilde{P}\rho(20\rho+9) + \tilde{P} - 60\rho - 7}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} - 10\tilde{P}(3\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} - 3)}{48[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \\
&- T_6(\xi) \kappa \frac{3\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} - 3}{192\sqrt{1-\xi^2}[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]}, \text{ for sharp edges} \\
f_1(\xi) &= U_0(\xi) \left\{ \frac{-15[\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(8\rho+5) + 16] - 2\tilde{P}^2[3\rho(40\rho+17) + 1]}{48[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \right. \\
&+ \left. \tilde{P} \frac{\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}[3\rho(40\rho+17) + 1] + 6(80\rho+17)}{48[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \right\} \\
&+ U_2(\xi) \left\{ \frac{5(\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(48\rho+5) + 288) + 18\tilde{P}^2(5\rho(16\rho+7) + 1)}{96[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \right. \\
&- \left. 3\tilde{P} \frac{\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(5\rho(16\rho+7) + 1) + 30(32\rho+7)}{96[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]} \right\} \\
&+ U_4(\xi) \frac{(3\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} - 3)(10\tilde{P} - \kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2})}{96[\tilde{P}(5\rho-1) - 5]}, \text{ for smooth edges}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{2n-1}(\xi) = & \left\{ T_0(\xi) \left\{ \frac{20n^4(\tilde{P}\rho - 1)[\tilde{P}(24\rho - 1) - 24] - 40n^3(\tilde{P}\rho - 1)[\tilde{P}(24\rho - 1) - 24]}{8n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3][\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \right. \right. \\
& + \frac{n^2[\tilde{P}(\tilde{P}(5\rho(24\rho - 17) - 3) - 240\rho + 85) + 120]}{8n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3][\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \\
& \left. \left. + \frac{n[\tilde{P}(\tilde{P}(5\rho(72\rho + 13) + 3) - 720\rho - 65) + 360] + 6\tilde{P}(-5\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} + 5)}{8n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3][\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \right\} \right. \\
& + T_2(\xi) \left\{ \frac{\kappa \left\{ -80n[4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3]\tilde{P}\rho^2 \right\} - 5\rho[(n-1)n(4(n-1)n(5\tilde{P} - 16) - 47\tilde{P} + 48) + 12\tilde{P}]}{64n(4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{\kappa \left[(n-1)n(100(n-1)n + 9\tilde{P} - 155) + 12(\tilde{P} + 5) \right]}{64n(4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \right\} \\
& + T_4(\xi) \frac{[4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - \tilde{P}(3\rho + 1) + 3] \left[\kappa(40\rho + 3) - 20\sqrt{1-\xi^2}\tilde{P} \right]}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}[\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \\
& + 80(n-1)n\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(24\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} - 24)(4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - \tilde{P}(3\rho + 1) + 3) \\
& \frac{32(2n-3)(2n+1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}[\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)} \\
& + T_6(\xi) \frac{\kappa[-4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) + 3\tilde{P}\rho + \tilde{P} - 3]}{64(2n-3)(2n+1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}[\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5]} \\
& - T_{2n}(\xi) \frac{\frac{\kappa[8(n-1)(2n+1)\rho + 3]}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} + 8(-2n + \frac{1}{n} + 1)\tilde{P}}{32(n-1)(2n+1)} \\
& T_{2n-2}(\xi) \frac{\frac{\kappa[8n(2n-3)\rho + 3]}{n\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} + \frac{8(3-2n)\tilde{P}}{n-1}}{32(2n-3)} - \frac{T_{2n-4}(\xi)\kappa}{32(2n^2 - 5n + 3)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \dots \\
& \left. \frac{T_{2n+2}(\xi)\kappa}{(64n^2 + 32n)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} - U_{2(n-1)}(\xi) \left[(2n-1)(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) \right] \right\}, \text{ for sharp edges} \\
f_{2n-1}(\xi) = & \left\{ -U_0(\xi) \left[\frac{5(2n-3)(2n+1)((n-1)n-1)\tilde{P}\rho - (n-1)n[20(n-1)n + \tilde{P} - 35] - 3(\tilde{P} + 5)}{8n(4(n-2)n^2 + n + 3)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \right] \right. \\
& \cdot (2\tilde{P} - \kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}) \\
& + U_2(\xi) \frac{5(4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - \tilde{P}(3\rho + 1) + 3) \left(-\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(16\rho + 1) + \tilde{P}(96\rho + 6) - 96 \right)}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\
& - U_4(\xi) \frac{(4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) - \tilde{P}(3\rho + 1) + 3) \left(10\tilde{P} - \kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2} \right)}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\
& + U_{2n}(\xi) \frac{-\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2} + 4n\tilde{P} + 2\tilde{P}}{32n^2 + 16n} \\
& + U_{2n-2}(\xi) \left[\frac{1}{2}\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}\rho + \frac{\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2} - 2\tilde{P}}{16n} + \tilde{P} \left(\frac{1}{8-8n} + \rho \right) + n(2 - 2\tilde{P}\rho) - 1 \right] \\
& \left. - U_{2n-4}(\xi) \frac{\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2} - 4n\tilde{P} + 6\tilde{P}}{32n^2 - 80n + 48} \right\}, \text{ for smooth edges}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_0(\xi) &= T_{-1}(\xi) \frac{\kappa(\tilde{P}(48\rho+3)-64)}{64\sqrt{1-\xi^2}\tilde{P}} + T_1(\xi) \left[\frac{\kappa(\tilde{P}(96\rho+7)-64)}{64\sqrt{1-\xi^2}\tilde{P}} - \frac{\tilde{P}}{2} \right] \\
&\quad T_3(\xi) \left[\frac{\tilde{P}}{2} - \frac{\kappa(48\rho+5)}{64\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \right] + T_5(\xi) \frac{\kappa}{64\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \\
&\quad + 6U_1(\xi)(1-\tilde{P}\rho), \text{ for sharp edges} \\
f_0(\xi) &= -\frac{\tilde{P}T_1(\xi)}{2} + \frac{\tilde{P}T_3(\xi)}{2} + U_1(\xi) \left[\frac{1}{8}\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(12\rho+1) - 6\tilde{P}\rho + 6 \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{32}\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}U_3(\xi), \text{ for smooth edges} \\
\\
f_{2n}(\xi) &= \left\{ T_{-1}(\xi) \frac{\kappa \left(64(n^2-1)^2\tilde{P}\rho + n^2(-64n^2-7\tilde{P}+128) - 5\tilde{P}-64 \right)}{64(4n^4-5n^2+1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}\tilde{P}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + T_1(\xi) \frac{\kappa(64n^4(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+n^2(128-\tilde{P}(176\rho+15))+\tilde{P}(112\rho+3)-64)}{(n^2-1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} + 96\tilde{P}^2 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + T_3(\xi) \frac{\frac{\kappa(48\rho+9)}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} - 32\tilde{P}}{64(4n^2-1)} + T_5(\xi) \frac{\kappa}{(64-256n^2)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + T_{2n+1}(\xi) \left\{ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4n+2} - \frac{\kappa(8(2n^2+n-1)\rho+3)}{32(2n^2+n-1)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \right\} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + T_{2n-1}(\xi) \frac{\frac{16(-2n^2+n+1)\tilde{P}}{2n-1} + \frac{\kappa(8(n-1)(2n+1)\rho+3)}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}}{32(n-1)(2n+1)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\kappa T_{2n+3}(\xi)}{(64n^2+96n+32)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} - \frac{\kappa T_{2n-3}(\xi)}{(64n^2-96n+32)\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + U_1(\xi) \frac{6-6\tilde{P}\rho}{1-4n^2} - U_{2n-1}(\xi)2n(\tilde{P}\rho-1) \right\}, \text{ for sharp edges} \\
f_{2n}(\xi) &= \left\{ U_1(\xi) \frac{-\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(6\rho+1)+4\tilde{P}(6\rho+1)-24}{16n^2-4} + U_3(\xi) \frac{8\tilde{P}-\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}{32-128n^2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + U_{2n+1}(\xi) \frac{-\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}+4n\tilde{P}+4\tilde{P}}{32n^2+48n+16} - U_{2n-3}(\xi) \frac{\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}-4n\tilde{P}+4\tilde{P}}{32n^2-48n+16} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{U_{2n-1}(\xi)}{16n^2-4} \left[\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}(1-2\rho) - 32n^3(\tilde{P}\rho-1) + 8\kappa\sqrt{1-\xi^2}n^2\rho \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + n(\tilde{P}(8\rho-4)-8) \right] \right\}, \text{ for smooth edges}
\end{aligned}$$

520 In order to apply the Galerkin procedure, the governing equation (43) is mul-
multiplied by $T_m(\xi)/\sqrt{1-\xi^2}$ or $T_m(\xi)$ with $m \in \mathbb{N}$ (for sharp and smooth edges
522 respectively) and integrated over the contact domain, i.e the equilibrium imposed
in a weak-form. Therefore, using integrals (40) and (41) provides the

524 governing equation in the usual eigen-system form,

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_{0,1} & f_{0,5} & \cdots & f_{0,2n-1} \\ f_{2,1} & f_{2,5} & \cdots & f_{2,2n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{m,1} & f_{m,5} & \cdots & f_{m,2n-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_5 \\ \vdots \\ C_{2n-1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \text{ for even case} \quad (44)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_{0,0} & f_{0,4} & \cdots & f_{0,2n} \\ f_{2,0} & f_{2,4} & \cdots & f_{2,2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{m,0} & f_{m,4} & \cdots & f_{m,2n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_0 \\ C_4 \\ \vdots \\ C_{2n} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \text{ for odd case} \quad (45)$$

namely

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (46)$$

526 where the components of the matrix \mathbf{A} , whose characteristic equation provides
the buckling load values, are defined by the scalar product between the vectors
528 $\mathbf{f}^{(i)}$ and \mathbf{t}_m , namely

$$\begin{aligned} f_{m,1} &= \mathbf{f}^{(1)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{m,Even}, & f_{m,2n-1} &= \mathbf{f}^{(2n-1)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{m,Even}, \\ f_{m,0} &= \mathbf{f}^{(0)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{m,Odd}, & f_{m,2n} &= \mathbf{f}^{(2n)} \cdot \mathbf{t}_{m,Odd}. \end{aligned}$$

The latter vectors contain the dimensionless parameters ρ and κ as well as the
530 dimensionless buckling load. In particular, they are defined as

- For sharp edges:

$$t_{m,Odd} = \{t_{-1,m}, t_{1,m}, t_{3,m}, t_{5,m}, t_{2n+1,m}, t_{2n-1,m}, t_{2n+3,m}, t_{2n-3,m},$$

$$l_{1,m}, l_{3,m}, l_{2n+1,m}, l_{2n-1,m}, r_{2n-1,m}, r_{1,m}\}$$

$$\mathbf{f}^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{64}\kappa\left(48\rho - \frac{64}{\tilde{P}} + 3\right) \\ \frac{1}{64}\kappa\left(96\rho - \frac{64}{\tilde{P}} + 7\right) \\ -\frac{1}{64}\kappa(48\rho + 5) \\ \frac{\kappa}{64} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\tilde{P}}{2} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{2} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 6 - 6\tilde{P}\rho \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{f}^{(2n)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\kappa\left((-64n^2 - 7\tilde{P} + 128)n^2 - 5\tilde{P} + 64(n^2 - 1)^2\tilde{P}\rho - 64\right)}{64(4n^4 - 5n^2 + 1)\tilde{P}} \\ \frac{\kappa(64(\tilde{P}\rho - 1)n^4 + (128 - \tilde{P}(176\rho + 15))n^2 + \tilde{P}(112\rho + 3) - 64)}{64(4n^4 - 5n^2 + 1)\tilde{P}} \\ \frac{3\kappa(16\rho + 3)}{64(4n^2 - 1)} \\ \frac{\kappa}{64 - 256n^2} \\ \frac{1}{32}\kappa\left(-8\rho - \frac{3}{2n^2 + n - 1}\right) \\ \frac{1}{32}\kappa\left(8\rho - \frac{3}{-2n^2 + n + 1}\right) \\ \frac{\kappa}{64n^2 + 96n + 32} \\ -\frac{\kappa}{64n^2 - 96n + 32} \\ \frac{3\tilde{P}}{8n^2 - 2} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{2 - 8n^2} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4n + 2} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{2 - 4n} \\ -2n(\tilde{P}\rho - 1) \\ \frac{6 - 6\tilde{P}\rho}{1 - 4n^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$t_{m,Even} = \{t_{2,m}, t_{4,m}, t_{6,m}, t_{0,m}, t_{2n,m}, t_{2n-2,m}, t_{2n+2,m}, t_{2n-4,m},$$

$$l_{0,m}, l_{2,m}, l_{4,m}, l_{6,m}, l_{2n-2,m}, l_{2n,m}, r_{2(n-1),m}\}$$

$$\mathbf{f}^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\kappa(5(96\rho + 35) - \tilde{P}(3\rho(160\rho + 69) + 5))}{192(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\ \frac{\kappa(3\rho(20\rho + 9)\tilde{P} + \tilde{P} - 60\rho - 7)}{48(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\ -\frac{\kappa(3\rho\tilde{P} + \tilde{P} - 3)}{192(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \tilde{P}\left(\frac{19\tilde{P}}{75\tilde{P}\rho - 15(\tilde{P} + 5)} + 2\rho + \frac{49}{40}\right) - 2 \\ \tilde{P}\left(\frac{58\tilde{P}}{75\tilde{P}\rho - 15(\tilde{P} + 5)} + 6\rho + \frac{37}{10}\right) - 6 \\ -\frac{5\tilde{P}(3\rho\tilde{P} + \tilde{P} - 3)}{24(\tilde{P}(5\rho - 1) - 5)} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{f}^{(2n-1)} = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa(235\tilde{P}\rho+9\text{Pt}-240\rho-155)}{64(4n^2-4n-3)(5\tilde{P}\rho-\text{Pt}-5)} - \frac{5\kappa(n-1)n(5\tilde{P}\rho-16\rho-5)}{16(4n^2-4n-3)(5\tilde{P}\rho-\text{Pt}-5)} + \frac{\kappa(\text{Pt}(5\rho(-4n(4(n-2)n^2+n+3)\rho-3)+3)+15)}{16n(4(n-2)n^2+n+3)(\text{Pt}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{\kappa(40\rho+3)(-\tilde{P}(3\rho+1)+4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+3)}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{\kappa(3\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)-3)}{64(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{32}\kappa\left(\frac{3}{-2n^2+n+1}-8\rho\right) \\ \frac{1}{32}\kappa\left(8\rho+\frac{3}{n(2n-3)}\right) \\ \frac{\kappa}{64n^2+32n} \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32(2n^2-5n+3)} \\ \frac{5(n-2)n^2(\text{Pt}\rho-1)(\text{Pt}(24\rho-1)-24)}{2(4(n-2)n^2+n+3)(\text{Pt}(5\rho-1)-5)} + \frac{3\tilde{P}(-5\tilde{P}\rho+\text{Pt}+5)}{4n(4(n-2)n^2+n+3)(\text{Pt}(5\rho-1)-5)} + \dots\text{SAME CEL} \\ \dots\text{SAME CELL} \frac{n^2(\text{Pt}(\text{Pt}(5\rho(24\rho-17)-3)-240\rho+85)+120)+n(\text{Pt}(\text{Pt}(5\rho(72\rho+13)+3)-720\rho-65)+360)}{8n(4(n-2)n^2+n+3)(\text{Pt}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{5(24\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-24)(-\tilde{P}(3\rho+1)+4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+3)}{4(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{5\tilde{P}(3\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)-3)}{8(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4-4n} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4n} \\ -(2n-1)(\tilde{P}\rho-1) \end{array} \right]$$

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where the terms $t_{i,j}$, $l_{i,j}$, $r_{i,j}$ and $g_{i,j}$ are known integral from eqns(38-41).

- For smooth edges:

$$\mathbf{t}_{m,Odd} = \{r_{2,m}, r_{4,m}, r_{2n-2,m}, r_{2n,m}, r_{2n+2,m}, g_{1,m}, g_{3,m}, g_{2n-1,m}, g_{2n-3,m}, g_{2n+1,m}\}$$

$$\mathbf{f}^{(0)} = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{1}{8}(12\rho\kappa + \kappa) \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \tilde{P}(-6\rho - \frac{1}{2}) + 6 \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{array} \right], \quad \mathbf{f}^{(2n)} = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{6\rho\kappa + \kappa}{4-16n^2} \\ \frac{\kappa}{32(4n^2-1)} \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32n^2-48n+16} \\ \frac{(8n^2-2)\rho\kappa + \kappa}{16n^2-4} \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32n^2+48n+16} \\ \frac{6\rho\tilde{P} + \tilde{P} - 6}{4n^2-1} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{4-16n^2} \\ -\frac{n(8(\tilde{P}\rho-1)n^2 + \tilde{P} - 2\tilde{P}\rho + 2)}{4n^2-1} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{8n-4} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{8n+4} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{t}_{Even} = \{r_{1,m}, r_{3,m}, r_{5,m}, r_{2n-1,m}, r_{2n+1,m}, r_{2n-3,m}, g_{0,m}, g_{2,m}, g_{4,m}, g_{2n-2,m}, g_{2n,m}, g_{2n-4,m}\}$$

$$\mathbf{f}^{(1)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{48} \kappa \left(-\frac{16\tilde{P}}{-5\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}+5} + 24\rho + 15 \right) \\ \frac{\kappa(5(48\rho+5)-3\tilde{P}(5\rho(16\rho+7)+1))}{96(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{\kappa(3\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-3)}{96(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{2\tilde{P}^2}{3(-5\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}+5)} - \frac{1}{8}(8\rho+5)\tilde{P} + 1 \\ \frac{3}{80}\tilde{P} \left(-\frac{56\tilde{P}}{-5\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}+5} + 80\rho + 51 \right) - 3 \\ -\frac{5\tilde{P}(3\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-3)}{48(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f}^{(2n-1)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{8} \kappa \left(\frac{4(n-2)(n+1)\tilde{P}}{(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} + \frac{1}{n-n^2} + 1 \right) \\ -\frac{5\kappa(16\rho+1)(-\tilde{P}(3\rho+1)+4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+3)}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{\kappa(-\tilde{P}(3\rho+1)+4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+3)}{32(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{1}{16} \kappa \left(8\rho + \frac{1}{(n-1)n} \right) \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32n^2+16n} \\ -\frac{\kappa}{32n^2-80n+48} \\ \frac{1}{4}\tilde{P} \left(-\frac{4(n-2)(n+1)\tilde{P}}{(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} + \frac{1}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n} - 1 \right) \\ \frac{15(16\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-16)(-\tilde{P}(3\rho+1)+4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)+3)}{16(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ \frac{5\tilde{P}(3\rho\tilde{P}+\tilde{P}-4(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1)-3)}{16(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)} \\ -\frac{16(2n-3)(2n+1)(\tilde{P}(5\rho-1)-5)}{(2n-1)(\tilde{P}+8(n-1)n(\tilde{P}\rho-1))} \\ \frac{8(n-1)n}{\tilde{P}} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{8n} \\ \frac{\tilde{P}}{8(n-1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

where the terms $g_{m,n}$ are defined in eqns (41).